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Index

Sl. No.	Paper Title	Author	Page No.
01	A Critical Understanding of Learning Management System	Solomon Arulraj DAVID	04-12
02	Guru versus Google	Kusum Jain & Shelly	13-21
03	Rashtriya Madhyamik Shikshya Abhiyan in North East India	Dr. Yodida Bhutia	22-32
04	Potentiality and Functions of National Knowledge Network (NKN) in India	Dr. Debasish Pradhan	33-43
05	Inclusive Education in India: A Demand on Teacher Preparation and Support	Prajnya Paramita Jena	44-61
06	Academic achievement of senior secondary students in relations to their personality type and achievement motivation	Dr. Jatinder Kumra	62-75

07	Effect of Students' Feedback and Academic Discipline of Teachers on Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary Teachers	Dr. S. K. Tyagi & Anupam Jain	76-98
08	Why Professionals Burnout: A Case of Teachers	Akhilesh	99-107
09	A Study of Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and academic Achievement among Student-Teachers	Dr. Pratik Upadhyaya	108-119
10	Health Education in India: An Immediate Need	D.R. Goel, Chhaya Goel,	120-156

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Paper-8

**Why Professionals Burnout: A Case of
Teachers**

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Why Professionals Burnout: A Case of Teachers

Akhilesh¹¹

Introduction-

The problem of burnout is certainly as old as stressful work environments and professional frustration. Earlier it was a hidden problem because, until recently, professionals had multiple options for dealing with their developing exhaustion (Paine, 1984). Increased stress on job due to changed professional trends aggravated the situation. So a sense of increasing dissatisfaction on job compounded by an awareness of decreasing options added to the occurrence of burnout.

The phenomenon of job burnout is not new, though the research in the field has got momentum recently. The literature has portrayed people working in various helping professions viz. teachers (Sahu, 1992; Lau, 2002; Cunningham, 2004; Trivedi, 2005; Denton, 2009; Durr, 2009; Tucker, 2009), school administrators (Barber, 2001; Hawkins, 2009; Ward, 2009), school counsellors (Rovero, 2004), social workers (Boston, 2009) medical practitioners (Dixit, 1992; Pradhan 1994) etc. are particularly susceptible to the burnout syndrome. The job related burnout has its genesis in human services and people work professions. Burnout probably has always been a problem in the human services but various social and political changes in the world have made people more aware of the problem now. Dixit (1992) opined that human service work involve direct responsibility for the wellbeing of other people so it has a personal significance to professionals engaged in human service professions. Their identity and self-esteem is more tied to the

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outcome of their work than that in other occupations. As preparation for these professions requires more inputs of time, money and intellect, so there develops an emotional bond between the professionals and their profession. Persons entering human service professions often have high needs for approval and heightened expectations from their profession. Their work serves in part, a means to gain social approval and enhance self-image, besides earning. They receive great pleasure from the results of their service. As the work becomes the primary means for enhancing self-concept, these persons often over commit their time and energy.

The seeds of burnout are contained in the assumption that the real world will be in harmony with dreams. Heightened level of expectations from work outcomes results in burnout. Many individuals enter a profession with a glorified, glamorous and heroic image of the profession in their mind. But in reality, the conditions of the profession are far from it. This mismatch between expectations and real conditions contribute to burnout. Cherniss (1980) listed five unrealistic assumptions about human service professions which contribute to burnout:

- (i) The belief that credentials equal competence and competence leads to a high degree of success to work.
- (ii) The expectation that professional status guarantees a high level of personal autonomy and control in one's work.
- (iii) Assumption that clients are both cooperative and grateful.
- (iv) Work is supposed to be intrinsically interesting, meaningful and stimulating.
- (v) The expectation that relations among co-workers will be supportive and collegial.

These faulty assumptions contribute to burnout in at least three ways. First, these create unrealistic expectations and goals in the professionals including teachers.

Second, these assumptions lead to unrealistic expectations in the clients and general public from professionals including teachers. The third way in which these unrealistic assumptions contribute to burnout is through their effects on institutional practices. Thus heightened expectations contribute to the seemingly high incidence of burnout.

Burnout among Teachers-

It is often said that teaching is one of the noble professions but the realities of classroom life and institutional environment have made teaching a stressful profession. Sources of stress on teachers include-role related stress, classroom indiscipline, students' apathy, difficulty in developing appropriate instructional material for students with special needs, lack of sufficient time for professional development, relationships with administrators, colleagues and parents, large classroom size, lack of resources, isolation, fear of violence, limited promotional opportunities, inadequate salaries, involuntary transfers, excessive paperwork etc. These demands of teaching can outweigh the resources of even the most dedicated teacher. Depletion and burnout have become serious realities for teachers (McMohan, 2004). Teacher burnout has created many problems for the teaching profession. Teacher burnout has been shown to have negative effects on teacher and student performance (Durr, 2009).

As a result many teachers are experiencing that their feelings about themselves, their students and their profession are becoming negative than they were initially. Such teachers do not derive any pleasure from teaching; rather they take it as a routine work. For them, teaching is no more a source of satisfaction. This develops among them a sense of frustration, loss of enthusiasm and alienation from job. These teachers are susceptible to developing chronic feelings of emotional

exhaustion and fatigue, negative attitude towards their students and a loss of feeling of accomplishment on the job (Trivedi 2005). No doubt, these are the symptoms of burnout.

The three types of behavioural reactions develop in burnout teachers. The first is development of chronic feelings of exhaustion. Teachers in this stage express feelings of being tired, irritable and emotionally drained. Emotionally exhausted teachers often develop negative, cynical attitudes towards their students. This change in attitude leads to the second behavioural symptom of burnout, depersonalisation. A teacher display depersonalised attitude by withdrawing from contact with students. The depersonalised attitude of the teacher is further reflected when he treats students as the impersonal objects, calling them derogatory names or using labels to describe individual students. The third aspect of teacher burnout occurs when teachers begin to feel they are no longer accomplishing anything worthwhile in their work.

The teacher education institutions do not provide real world view and expectations to pre-service teachers or pupil-teachers. There is a contradiction between the socialisation of teachers by teacher education institutions and the role required in schools. Pre-service teachers expect that they will instruct and shape young minds, plan and develop curricula, evaluate students, and manage classrooms and maintain discipline. They expect that they will be granted the professional autonomy to exert control over the roles they are assigned to perform. But professional autonomy in the real world of teaching is significantly restricted. Teacher's capacity to perform effectively is significantly compromised by overcrowded classrooms, under staffed colleges, some times less than eager students, complex bureaucracy and separate policy formation form policy

implementation. Often students challenge the authority of teachers in and out of the classroom. Policies which determine textbooks, course content and even the pedagogy of information delivery are also removed from teachers' control. There is difference between the new methodologies created and taught in teacher-training institutions and those permitted in educational institutions. Often schools are adhered to older practices of teaching. These all factors create stress in work environment of educational institutions and this leads to role alienation and burnout.

How to Prevent Burnout-

As burnout results from the interaction of people and environment, there are two ways to reduce burnout in institutions: by strengthening individual resources to cope with stress in their work setting and reducing the demands and stress that individuals experience in their environment.

Pines (1984) recognised four specific sites for intervention against burnout: individual, interpersonal, workplace and organisational.

1. Individual level interventions to strengthen an individual's ability to deal with job related stress.
2. Interpersonal level interventions to strengthen interpersonal relations or workgroup dynamics either to decrease stress or to support individual's abilities to deal with stress.
3. Workplace related interventions intended to reduce stress or ameliorate it in some way.
4. Organisational level interventions to bring change in policies, procedures or structure of the organisational factors related to burnout.

Wilder & Plutchik (1984) and Edelwich & Brodsky (1984) suggested inclusion of burnout preventive intervention component in teacher training programmes. Leiter & Maslach (2005) suggested three ways to reduce the incidence of burnout: change the individual, change the organisation or change the relationship between organisation and individual.

Interventions Designed for the Institutions-

It is easier to restructure a role than to restructure the character of either an individual or society. Prevention of burnout is far more effective and less costly than its treatment. So, changes should be introduced in the structure, policies and work procedures of the organisation/ institutions in order to mitigate or eliminate stress and frustrations emanating from the work environment (Carroll & White, 1984).

Interventions Designed for the Individuals-

The foremost step in intervention is giving a relief from stress on the job to the affected individual. This may be done by giving the person time off away from the institution, allocating less stressful job within the institution or to reduce his/her workload. The importance of good physical and mental health can't be ignored in treating job burnout. So, thorough physical examination and personal counseling is recommended. Stress management techniques and need gratification skills could also help in this regard.

Conclusion-

A burnout teacher cannot perform his duties adequately. So, all the possible measures should be taken to reduce the occurrence of burnout and efforts for mitigating burnout among the teachers. A satisfied teacher can only satisfy the

students and can groom them for their bright future. Educational institutions need to be restructured so that teachers may feel satisfied with the institutions.

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